

Best Practice Guide for Postdoctoral Research Programmes

Based on findings from the implementation of REinforcing Women In REsearch (REWIRE), an EU MSCA COFUND hosted by the DLE Research Services and Career Development, University of Vienna

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INTRODUCTION

Here we offer input on best practice in planning and implementing postdoctoral researcher (PDR) training programmes in a higher-education setting. This guide is based on our experience running two successful Marie Skłodowska-Curie Action (MSCA) COFUNDS: INDICAR (2013-2018); and Reinforcing Women in Research, REWIRE (2019-2025). The planning and delivery of REWIRE drew directly on the experiences from INDICAR.

Implementing both COFUNDS has presented many opportunities for learning. And while the outcomes have been overwhelmingly successful – 24 of 28 fellows have gone on either to permanent positions or to hold prestigious grants – there have been several accompanying challenges.

This guide aims to provide input useful to any organisation planning to host and implement a PDR programme. The content is drawn from a wealth of day-to-day administrative experiences, as well as formal meetings and encounters, in-programme training events and stakeholder feedback. This information has been subsequently refined down to what we consider the key points, which are presented here in a broad enough way to be more readily applied and/or adapted to other PDR training programmes. The division of the main part of this guide into three sections (pre-recruitment, recruitment and implementation) and the sub-divisions within these parts, reflects the practical experience of the REWIRE programme, upon which this publication is based.

Before focusing specifically on recruitment and implementation, we begin with 3 guiding principles, which we believe lie at the heart of any similar training programme:

MANAGEMENT OF EXPECTATIONS

Several key stakeholders will be participating: the unit organizing/coordinating the PDR training programme; the PDRs; the supervisors/mentors; the departments where the PDRs are based; the funder; the Host Institution (HI) leadership. Each stakeholder comes with their own set of expectations, and it is vital that the organizing unit, at application-writing stage, begins to consider these.

COMMUNICATION

Good communication between all stakeholders within a PDR programme is essential to its success. When planning a programme, make communication a priority. Identify who the stakeholders are and to what extent the programme management team (PMT) will be an axis for intra-programme communication. Thereafter, devise robust measures and methods to enable as optimal-as-possible communication between stakeholders. Also keep in mind that stakeholders may have differing interpretations of terms or terminology, e.g. ‘mentor’ and ‘supervisor’. Finally, if a PDR programme includes international participants make sure where at all possible that key documents (e.g. employment contracts) and programme information are presented in a language well understood by all stakeholders.

AGILITY & CAPACITY TO BE RESPONSIVE

PDR programmes inevitably encounter unexpected events, and to be successful they need to respond effectively to these. Aim therefore for an agile programme structure, flexible enough in key points/nodes to allow for adaptation.

1. PRE-RECRUITMENT

1.1. PROGRAMME PURPOSE

Be very clear about the programme's aims and limits. Communicate these explicitly in all recruitment-related activities with stakeholders; make sure there is also a common understanding of them within the PMT. Pay particular attention to signposting any prominent focus/expectations within the programme, e.g. the relative balance between PDRs' career development vs. their scientific research; under what conditions part-time working is possible.

From the outset, ensure any structural limits are clearly communicated from the beginning, and recorded in formats easily accessible to all stakeholders e.g. on the programme website. If possible, include provision for each PDR to have their own research budget, and be mindful of how the budget amount and/or any conditions on its use might restrict PDRs depending on what discipline they are in.

1.2. WHO ARE THE PDRS?

Clearly define your target group. Care, however, is needed in the construction of programme, so that the aims/parts of the planned programme really do engage/recruit the optimal target group.

If recruitment across different disciplines is intended, remain aware that research-related costs vary considerably with regard to field. Define recruitment parameters carefully to engage the intended target group.

1.3. HOW TO IDENTIFY & THEN SELECT SUPERVISORS/MENTORS

Supervisors/mentors involvement within a PDR programme may vary widely, and relatedly their depth of engagement with PDRs and other stakeholders (including the PMT), from the recruitment phase onwards. Consider offering specific training for would-be supervisors/mentors, as well as within-programme mechanisms for checking in with them directly for feedback as well as for any trouble shooting.

From REWIRE's conception as a PDR programme, the term 'mentor' (rather than 'supervisor') was consciously chosen because it is more common within training contexts. However, no substantive difference in meaning was intended between 'mentor' and 'supervisor' and REWIRE fellows were, in effect, postdocs within a given research group, subject to the normal rules and hierarchies of authority that operated within that group. During implementation, positive and negative effects arose due to different interpretations among fellows of the terms 'supervisor' and 'mentor'. Consider carefully, therefore, the terms used in all programme-related materials, and if necessary, from the outset offer clear grounds to all relevant stakeholders for the choices made.

Consider also separating supervisor and mentor roles – i.e. supervisor as scientific guide, mentor for career development. Finally, bear in mind potential advantages of PDR and mentor having research topics close but not so close that they can interfere with project outcomes, e.g. who takes primary credit in publications etc. (For further guidance see: [MSCA Guidelines on Supervision](#)).

1.4. ADMINISTRATIVE STRUCTURE & MANAGEMENT LINES, INCLUDING, IF RELEVANT, INTERNAL UNITS WITHIN THE HI AS WELL AS ANY EXTERNAL STAKEHOLDERS

- 1) How is administrative responsibility of PDRs shared within a given programme? What are the management lines? How centralized the administration and management of a PDR programme may well depend on how its funding is held and distributed within an HI.
- 2) Be mindful that HI structures and administration practices, including how grants are disbursed, might yield unintended negative effects on the perceived 'home' of the PDR.

- 3) From the PDRs perspective, who do they 'belong' to? The supervisor/mentor's research/lab group? Or the employing unit, if different from the hosting department? If the latter, are they more separate – in their status and thus their research project?
- 4) The PDR-supervisor/mentor relationship is the primary one and will likely have most influence on the PDR's experience of their time at the HI as well as impacting on their subsequent trajectory post-programme, e.g. via references. We suggest promoting PDR-supervisor/mentor contact ahead of any application; in our experience prior exchanges (including meetings, if possible) can help in building rapport as well as establishing and exploring expectations on either side (e.g. regarding authorship and/or costs of any publications completed by the PDR during the programme).
- 5) Ensure regular check ins and updates with internal units – e.g. Human Resources (HR), Equality, Diversity & Inclusivity office (EDI), Open Access (OA) office etc. – involved in the PDR programme, including any expectations from either side re: participation. Check with host departments that all necessary equipment, expertise and administrative support is available at departmental level for the planned PDR project(s).
- 6) At application stage outline a reasonably clear training plan covering the programme's duration. This plan will require – in-built – relative flexibility and agility, enabling alterations *during* the programme, in response to feedback from stakeholders and/or structural changes.
- 7) *Force majeure* can occur. Plan for what you can, e.g. have several options for possible trainings available to implement, at fairly short notice.

1.5. ANTICIPATING UNEXPECTED PROBLEMS

The PMT should have a (written) process for how to work with PDRs facing difficulties, especially when these problems fall outside the PMT's expertise or responsibility, so that potential issues are handled consistently and as effectively as possible. Such a written process needs to include clear guidance about what falls within the PMT's responsibility, and what is beyond its scope/capacity, and thus what other offices/officers within the HI the PDR can be referred to.

2. RECRUITMENT

2.1. ADVERTISING & DISSEMINATION

Standard procedures may exist within the HI. Depending on the funder, other sites or resources may also be specified or recommended. Programmes with specific theme(s)/foci may make other avenues, e.g. industry, fruitful sites for recruitment. Concise yet clear communication of the eligibility requirements in all advertisement and dissemination activities is crucial, as is an efficient and robust enquiry-filtering system.

2.2. ACCESSING & CHECKING DEPARTMENTAL PROVISION AT APPLICATION STAGE

Where specific equipment/facilities are required by a research project, if possible, enable the applicant to visit the department/lab, to better ensure expectations are managed early and on both (applicant and HI) sides. In addition, check with host departments, that the necessary expertise and administration support is available at departmental level for the planned PDR project(s).

2.3. EVALUATION OF APPLICATIONS

Consider how digital and human elements can best be utilized, based on the resources available in the HI, e.g. adaptation of existing application filtering processes, including use of databases. Make sure also that the format of the submission is appropriate for all subject disciplines being recruited to (e.g. Word format documents are less well-suited for mathematical figures and formulae than pdf documents).

3. IMPLEMENTATION

3.1. ONBOARDING

From the outset, communicate clearly (via email and in formal programme documents) roles of all the stakeholders, i.e. PMT, PDRs, supervisors/mentors, departmental administrators, funder(s). Written guidance should also be in place, detailing the responsibilities of other HI elements involved, e.g. HR department, PDR'S department etc. We recommend including a signed document between the supervisor/mentor, host department and the individual PDR detailing their 'rights and responsibilities/duties'; ask HR for support when drafting this to avoid misinterpretations and to ensure alignment with employment law etc. If PDRs have individual research budgets, communicate any conditions clearly and secure signed confirmation that these are understood by all relevant parties. In addition, in text/email form, send a specific communication to mentors outlining their expected role, including their 'duty of care' responsibilities such as ensuring their PDR takes holiday.

3.1.1. INTEGRATION OF PDRS INTO THEIR HOST DEPARTMENTS

Structural factors, e.g. HI administration processes and management lines, influence the integration of PDRs into host dept/research group. The PDR-supervisor/mentor relationship is also a core variable within the integration process. Nevertheless, factors beyond the HI's control can exist or occur, e.g. national/global economic or political changes.

3.2. PDR/PMT ENCOUNTERS

3.2.1. WELCOME MEETING

Depending on the programme, PDRs may start all at the same time, in a rolling fashion or as cohorts, which impacts on how each PDR is 'onboarded' into the programme. Individualized meetings offer a personalized welcome and enable response to specific questions but are organizationally complex and inefficient for communicating information relevant to all PDRs, especially if several begin at once. Group welcome meetings, although less personalized, enable new starters to begin to connect directly with each other.

Consider who should be present at this meeting: PDR, a PMT member +/- the supervisor/mentor? Thereafter keep in mind *how* PDRs will be formally interacted with and their progress monitored subsequently, and by *whom*. Regular Career Development meetings incorporating an updateable instrument, e.g. a 'living' Career Development Plan (CDP), can be effective in enabling PDR, supervisor/mentor and PMT to identify progress made over a given period as well as areas requiring additional attention and/or support.

3.2.2. TRAININGS

The PDR cohort's training needs will be predicated on the kind of programme being offered. And at least an outline of anticipated trainings is needed before programme implementation. At implementation stage give attention to how the trainings will run. Are rooms readily available? What cost implications may exist, including for trainers? Bear in mind PDRs with specific access limitations (e.g. wheel-chair users, hearing problems etc.), as well as the language of the training. At the programme's outset consider, together with all PDRs, establishing an agreed 'code of conduct' (CoC) regarding how to engage with trainers and colleagues, e.g. use of non-violent communication, active listening etc., and provide guidance on how conflicts should be handled and by whom, e.g. PMT members, trainers or peers. Prospective trainers could receive this CoC ahead of the event. A CoC can also serve to make clear trainer's needs/preferences (e.g. to host the training alone, or for a PMT member to be chair/moderator) and enable a mutual feedback flow between trainers, PDRs and PMT.

The content of trainings needs to be appropriate to the attendees; where a PDR cohort comprises various different disciplines/experience levels, consider sub-dividing training offers accordingly. Also,

some activities, e.g. more personalized career planning, might not be possible via single, targeted trainings. Instead, individualized input, e.g. career coaching, could be more effective.

3.2.3. RETREATS

Consider including a retreat at the programme's start and potentially recurring at regular (e.g. yearly) intervals thereafter, where PDRs, PMT and possibly supervisors/mentors gather. Different from workshops or standard trainings, their aim is more diverse: to facilitate a sense of cohesion/belonging among the PDRs and to the programme and HI; for active knowledge exchange, including trainings but also between PDRs, who may have wide and varied prior professional experience; for the PMT to interact directly with the PDR group as a whole, which can yield very different results from more individual encounters, e.g. at Career Development meetings.

3.2.4. EXIT INTERVIEWS & SURVEYS

Exit interviews, between PMT and PDR, are a useful formal marker of a postdoc's time in the programme. These interviews also allow reflection and feedback on the PDR's experience as a whole, a different process than the outcome from regular PMT/PDR interactions during the postdoc position, e.g. CDP meetings. Exit surveys and interviews are valuable: online surveys gather more general data about the PDR's experience; in-person interviews enable a more open, discursive encounter. In both cases important information can be gathered to help the PMT understand what worked well within the programme, and what could be improved going forward – if possible within the existing programme. In any case, data yielded can inform better planning of future PDR programmes hosted by the HI. The interviews also give the chance, hopefully, for PDR and PMT to end the relationship in a way that communicates mutual understanding and appreciation, even where feedback from the PDR has not necessarily been positive.

3.2.5. INFORMAL GROUP INTERACTIONS

Informal social events can be helpful for PDRs and PMT to get to know each other, especially at the programme's start; and where some PDRs are new to the country as well as to the HI they can be even more valuable. Also consider encouraging PDRs to create their own network of communication and support both within the programme cohort(s) as well as with other PDRs within (but not necessarily limited to) their respective departments.

3.3. PMT & ADMINISTRATION

As discussed, implementation of PDR programme budget depends on the HI's structure and administrative practices as well as specific funder requirements. It is worth restating the need to consider the extent to which the programme is centrally administered and/or elements devolved to relevant departments. Moreover, changes/flexibility in processes can arise during the programme's implementation. Maintaining clear, positive communication lines between PMT and PDRs' departments (and other relevant stakeholders, e.g. the finance department) usually enables requests and/or changes to be more effectively handled by all concerned.

3.3.1. STRUCTURE & COMMUNICATION WITHIN THE PMT

Already at programme planning stage, consider what kind of PMT is needed. This will depend on the administrative tasks required at the programme's planning phase as well as during implementation. Once the PMT structure is known, keep in mind the communication flows between members, and where these might be formalized, e.g. through regular meetings. Employee 'churn' within large institutions is commonplace, but service delivery within PDR programmes needs to remain as reliable as possible. Therefore, where changes within a PMT occur, ensure job descriptions and expectations of different PMT roles are from the outset very clear, to preserve a consistent-as-possible function of the team internally as well as in relation to the other PDR programme stakeholders.

3.3.2. REALLOCATION OF RESOURCES IF THEY BECOME AVAILABLE DURING PROGRAMME

PDRs may leave the programme earlier than planned, e.g. after securing funding or another position more beneficial to their career trajectory, e.g. tenure-track position, or major third-party funding. Depending on funder requirements, reallocation of resources attributed to that PDR to other intra-programme aspects may be possible, enabling, for example, more training opportunities, or positions of remaining PDRs to be proportionally extended. In the latter case, consider prior to the programme start how such reallocation will be done: will it be offered to all remaining PDRs? Or will those who have performed well (e.g. secured subsequent funding, won prizes for their research etc.) be prioritized? Whatever the basis for reallocation, it should be communicated clearly to all PDRs when starting their position, e.g. within a 'right and responsibilities' contract, signed by the PDR, supervisor/mentor and host department.

3.4. REPORTING

Report(s) to the funder(s) regarding running and outcomes of a programme are a usual requirement. At the planning stage it is therefore crucial to record and communicate clearly to all relevant stakeholders any programme deliverables and milestones already known. Furthermore, delineate within the PMT (and stakeholders if necessary) a clear-as-possible timeframe for any reports, including who is responsible for associated tasks/ preparation of data etc. This information and delineation must be revisited where changes to reporting timelines/requirements or to the PMT take place. Ahead of reporting deadlines make sure to liaise early with involved stakeholders, e.g. PDRs, Finance dept. etc. Consider building into the programme timetable suitable reminders for making reporting information requests.

It is usual for many PDR outputs (journal articles etc.) to be ready for submission to potential publishers towards and/or just after the end of their fellowship/position. Be mindful therefore of any conditions regarding the use of publication agreements by the PDR (e.g. requirement of valid HI employment contract at point of submission), as well as funder publishing requirements (e.g. OA) and costs, which can vary considerably between disciplines.

4. CONCLUDING THOUGHTS

Reinforcing Women In REsearch, which ended in May 2025, was designed to benefit both PDRs recruited to the programme as well as the HI, and it has delivered very positively for both: it has enabled career progression for all its PDRs, and it continues to impact postdoc training and practices at HI, national and international levels.

REWIRE showcased how to recruit the best PDR candidates internationally and in a more transparent manner. For the HI, the programme has been a learning experience, towards optimising future PDR training programmes at the HI, but also potentially beyond – the aim of this Best Practice Guide.

In its implementation, REWIRE acted as a laboratory: for effective and efficient administration of PDR programmes; and towards developing an effective model for PDR positions, in particular the balance between research independence and integration within a department research group/lab and the positive effects PDRs having their own research budget.

As intended (and anticipated, based on the HI's prior experience with INDICAR), participation in REWIRE has resulted in all its PDRs progressing in their fields, 75% already continuing their academic careers at a higher level and/or with further prestigious funding – with more likely to follow.

At the University of Vienna, REWIRE has played an influential role within founding of the HI's Postdoc centre (<https://postdocs.univie.ac.at/>), and the PMT continue to contribute there and to other HI-based postdoc-related activities. REWIRE has also enabled those tasked with implementing PDR programmes and services to better understand how supervision at the PDR level works, e.g. what being a supervisor/mentorship is and is not; factors to bear in mind when selecting/recruiting supervisors and/or mentors and thereafter, throughout the PDRs' time on the programme. Through dissemination activities related to REWIRE, the PMT have also contributed to, and continue to be part of, ongoing debates about postdoc education within and beyond the HI, making impact at regional, national and international levels.

REWIRE has been a clear success, and this guide is a distillation of what we have learned along the way during its implementation. Through its creation and publication, this guide is intended to offer a very well-informed yet user-friendly resource for anyone working with PDR training programmes in higher education.

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

BPG – Best Practice Guide

CoC – Code of Conduct

CDP – Career Development Plan

EC – European Commission

EDI – Equality, Diversity & Inclusivity

HR – Human Resources

HI – Host Institution

MSCA – Marie Skłodowska-Curie Action

OA – Open Access

PDR – Postdoctoral Researcher

PMT – Programme Management Team

REA – Research Executive Agency

REWIRE – Reinforcing Women in Research